

Speculation on Radiation from a Moving Charge Part IV

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In a previous note (Part III), we argued that the classical analysis (1) of radiation emitted from an accelerating charge matches the quantum mechanical formalism of a quantum bound particle. In particular, the leading order term of the electric field (of order $1/r$ where r is the distance from a fixed origin to the measurement point) is expressed in terms of a Fourier series in $\exp(i\omega t)$.

$\exp(i\omega t)$ represents a photon wavefunction of frequency/momentum ω . E is the electric field and represents a classical measurable with E^2 being proportional to energy emitted per solid angle per time. This energy should be in the form of photons, yet the photons "interfere" to create E . In (1), a photon distribution is calculated for the time range: $-\infty$ to ∞ . Thus, a single photon distribution holds for the entire time range, one does not have a photon distribution at each point in time, even though there is a rate of energy emitted at each time. Furthermore, each photon when measured should carry with it a time of measurement. Thus, in a tiny range of t_1 , there should be a set of ω 's, yet one may not add these as scalars to obtain the energy emitted at time t_1 . We argue in this note that this is due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. The fact that certain ω 's (photons) are measured at t_1 does not mean they are associated with $E(t_1)$. A photon creating E at a particular time t_1 i.e. interfering with other photons is not necessarily associated with t_1 because of the uncertainty principle. Thus, we argue that this classical analysis seems to demonstrate a main feature of quantum mechanics.

Similar ideas hold for a bound quantum particle. One has a momentum distribution at each x i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, but one cannot know p and x with certainty. Thus, one cannot have a set of p measurements at x and assume that kinetic energy is $p^2/2m$ times its real frequency. Rather one has a complex conditional probability $\exp(ipx)a(p)/W$ with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ taking on positive and negative values.

Quantum Particle in a Bound State

One may consider $\exp(ipx)$ to represent the wavefunction of a free quantum particle. If a potential is introduced, we argue that $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ i.e. the particle receives stochastic hits. The system is treated statistically, so at each x one has a momentum distribution of free particle wavefunctions, but with weights which do not change with x i.e.

$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$, the normalization constant is called the wavefunction ((1))

At each point x , the conditional probability leads to a conservation of energy equation:

$$[\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Thus, there is a link with classical physics, but there is also a “break” with classical physics in the sense that $P(p/x)$ is complex. Even if one considers the real part of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$, it may be both positive and negative which breaks with usual probability theory. In other words, interference occurs at x . This is not simply a mathematical procedure because this interference leads to humps and troughs in $W(x)$ which also appear in $W(x)W(x)$, the physical density i.e. a physical measurable. This, it seems, is linked with Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle.

Imagine that one takes an ensemble of bound state particles (all in the ground state) and measures the momentum at x of each. This would lead to a set of p_i ’s all at x , but the probability would be real. Classically, there would be no interference if one calculated $\sum_i p_i^2/2m$ real frequency and this would not represent the quantum value of average kinetic energy at x . Thus, it seems one cannot really know the exact position of p because it is associated with a wavelength $1/p$ in $\exp(ipx)$. This is related to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. We argue in the next section that this idea also applies to photons emitted from an accelerating charge.

Radiation From an Accelerating Charge

The objective of a calculation of radiation emitted from an accelerating charge is to first calculate $E(r,t)$ and $B(r,t)$, electric and magnetic fields respectively, at a point r (vector) measured from a fixed origin at time t . Thus, ϕ and A the electric and magnetic potentials must be calculated based on a charge density source for ϕ and a current qv (v =velocity) for A . A key idea is to evaluate the sources at an earlier time than t , namely $t-R/c$ where R is the distance from the accelerating charge to the measuring point. R may then be expressed approximately in terms of r . One may see that an argument of $t-R/c$ (expanded about $t-r/c$) allows for both d/dt (partial) and d/dr to act upon it in basically the same manner (except for a factor of $1/c$, but $c=1$), thus $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ and $B = \text{grad } \times A$ all essentially yield a term of $a(t-r/c)$ where a is acceleration. In other words, d/dt and d/dr do not operate on $1/R$ which exists in both expressions for ϕ and A . ($\phi(r,t-R/c)$ and when expanded yields one term proportional to $v(t-r/c)$ which then becomes $a(t-r/c)$ upon action of $-\text{grad}$.)

Given E and B , one may calculate: $\text{Integral grad dot } (E \times B)$ volume (Poynting vector) which becomes a surface integral. For a sphere, area goes as rr while $E \times B$ goes as $1/(rr)$. Thus, there is nonzero emitted flux even at a large radius from the charge. This is said to be EM radiation or photons. At this point, the calculation is purely classical, although there are papers (2) which argue that Maxwell’s laws for E and B are really quantum mechanical, with $E+iB$ being the vector wavefunction of a photon. One does not, however, have Heisenberg uncertainty issues at this step.

In (1), the question is asked: What is the photon frequency distribution? This immediately leads to a quantum mechanical scenario because the photon is modeled by $\exp(i\omega t)$. In other words, a Fourier transform is made of E , but it is explicitly assumed that a photon is described by $\exp(i\omega t)$. This immediately leads to the idea of “interference” as different $\exp(i\omega_i t)$ with time independent weight interfere to create the electric field $E(r,t)$.

At this point, matters seem to become a little confusing. The energy radiated per time per solid angle is proportional to E^*E . One would expect that the energy emitted during a Δt at t_1 consists of photons which have a range of frequencies ω_i . In such a case, one would simply add the ω_i values. Each t_i would then have its own ω_i distribution. This, however, contradicts the

interference scenario: $E = \sum w A(w) \exp(iwt)$ and also the fact that $A(w)$ does not depend on time. Thus, (1) $A(w)$ is calculated which is related to $A(w)A(w)$ a distribution over all time (from -infinite to infinite). One is no longer interested in the energy release per time, but in the total energy released which is given in (1) as $d \text{ energy} / d \text{ solid angle} = \int dw A(w)A(w)$.

$A(w)A(w)$ is the probability of finding a photon with energy/momentum w at any time. When measuring, however, it seems that one may assign a time to each photon measurement. Why then cannot one add all photons associated with a time t_1 in order to find the energy emitted at t_1 ? In this note, we argue that quantum effects are present in this seemingly classical calculation. In particular, we argue that using $\exp(iwt)$ in a Fourier series of E (i.e. introducing photons), also introduces Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and the idea of a probability wave in w, t . Thus, measuring a photon at time t_1 does not mean that it was part of E at t_1 . There is time uncertainty with each photon because w is considered to be known precisely. Thus, the best one may do is to calculate the distribution of w over all time. This is exactly what is done in (1) i.e. $A(w)A(w)$ where $E = 1/\sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14} \int dw A(w) \exp(iwt)$. This is also what is done in quantum mechanics. (Alternatively, one may argue that energy from E is created due to the interference of photons. The two ideas seem to be the same.)

For a bound particle in a potential, one calculates the total integrated kinetic energy: $\int dp p^2/2m a(p)a(p)$. $a(p)a(p)$ represents the probability to find the particle in a state with momentum p anywhere in x i.e. x is completely unknown because p is known precisely. This seems to be the same situation which occurs for radiation emitted from an accelerating charge. One may consider conditional probabilities such as $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, but this is complex. Even if one takes the real part i.e. $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$, this probability is both positive and negative. Thus, there is interference which seems to be equivalent to the idea of an uncertainty principle. One has to be careful in interpreting a reading of momentum p at x , because the position of p is at least uncertain within a wavelength. With Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, exact knowledge of p means no knowledge of x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a classical calculation from (1) which involves expanding the electric field of an accelerating charge in terms of $\exp(iwt)$ i.e. photons ($E = \sum w A(w) \exp(iwt)$) is really a quantum mechanical calculation. $A(w)$ does not contain time and $A(w)A(w)$ is the energy probability related to the photon frequency w over the entire time range. Given that energy radiated per time per solid angle is proportional to E^*E , one may ask: What is the photon w (frequency) distribution at each t ? It seems one cannot determine this because the photons "interfere" to create E which in turn creates the energy rate through E^*E . This is equivalent, we argue, to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Even if one may measure a photon frequency at a time (say t_1), because of the probability wave $\exp(iwt)$, it does not mean that t_1 is associated with $E(t_1)$. There is uncertainty in the photon time within E . This is the same situation that occurs for a bound quantum particle. The probability to find a momentum p through all x is $a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. What is the probability to find a momentum p at x ? It is the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which is complex. Even taking the real part leads to $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ which has positive and negative values unlike a classical case. Thus, one uses the Heisenberg uncertainty

statement to say that one if one knows p one does not know x , (although the conditional probability allows for calculations).

In this note, we argue that a seemingly classical calculation (1) of photon frequencies from an accelerating charge seems to be a quantum problem with the Heisenberg uncertainty principle being a main feature forcing the w distribution to be over all time and not instantaneous. What seems to be interesting in this problem is that measurements of photons should be associated with a time of measurement, but this time does not seem to match time of emission. In other words, one cannot simply add w_i 's measured at t_1 to determine the energy emitted at t_1 .

References

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